

broken using boiling water. We studied the effect of boiling water treatment for varying times on the germinability of seeds of *S. rostrata*.

Welldeveloped seeds were selected, 50/set, and treated with 98 °C water for

15-180 s at intervals of 15 s. Treated seeds and untreated seeds were arranged on filter paper, placed in petri dishes, and moistened with distilled water. The germination test was carried out at room temperature (27-30 °C).

Treatment with boiling water increased germination from 4 to 78% with 75-s treatment (see table). Boiling water treatment beyond 75 s began to deform seeds. □

Crop management

Effect of sowing and planting method on rice yield

D. Rout and A. Mishra, Agronomy Department, OUAT, Bhubaneswar 751003; and T. Barik, Regional Research Station, Bhawanipatna 766001, Orissa, India

Performance of two dwarf and one tall indica varieties—OR152-2-17, Pratap, and Mahsuri, all with 135-140 d duration—was compared under different sowing and planting methods during 1982 wet season.

Treatments were broadcast seeding with and without *beushaning* (operating narrow wooden plow in standing crop under 10-15 cm standing water 30-35 d after germination), line sowing sprouted seeds in puddled soil, line transplanting, and skip-row planting with full and 75% recommended fertilizer (80-40-40 kg NPK/ha). The design was split plot with varieties in the main plots and sowing or transplanting method as subplots, with

Influence of sowing and transplanting methods on yield and yield attributes of rice. Orissa, India, 1982 kharif.

Sowing or planting method	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Cost of cultivation (\$/ha)	Net profit (\$/ha)
Broadcast seeding	298	82	19.7	3.4	156	246
Broadcast seeding followed by beushaning	265	83	20.2	3.2	175	210
Line sowing sprouted seeds 15 cm apart	313	82	20.3	3.8	185	264
Transplanting at 15- × 10-cm spacing	344	83	20.0	4.3	232	285
Skip-row (3:1) transplanting with 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha	290	87	20.4	4.3	202	314
Skip-row (3: 1) transplanting with 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha	295	85	20.6	4.3	221	295
SE (m) ±	5	1	0.3	0.1	—	—
LSD (0.05)	16	3	ns	0.2	—	—

three replications.

Soil of the experimental site was sandy loam with pH 6.1. Total N content was 0.031%, 17.3 kg available P/ha, and 104 kg available K/ha.

The interaction between variety and planting method was not significant. Grain yields under normal line planting, skip-row planting with 75% normal fertilizer, and skip-row planting with

normal fertilizer were not statistically different (see table). Skip-row planting with 75% normal fertilizer produced the highest net profit, followed by skip-row planting with full fertilizer. These methods saved 25% of the cost seedlings or fertilizers. Broadcast seeding followed by *beushaning* produced the lowest grain yield and net profit, probably because of low plant population. □

Selecting rice varieties for double transplanting in flood-affected areas

B. K. Singh, Agronomy Department, Rajendra Agricultural University, Pusa 813210, Bihar (present address: National Agricultural Research Project, RAU Campus, Bihar Agricultural College, Sabour 813210, Bihar), India

Large areas on the riverbanks in northeastern India frequently become flooded two to three times during the wet season, severely damaging the rice crop. Some farmers risk transplanting

rice in early Jul. If flooding comes late or is mild, the transplanted crop suffers least. Most farmers, however, do not want to risk transplanting early because they cannot afford to manage seedlings for retransplanting if the Jul crop is flooded. They usually transplant in Sep, when the chance of flooding ceases.

Two types of seedlings—conventional seedlings brought directly from the first nursery and kharuhan seedlings uprooted from the first nursery and transplanted closely in a second nursery—are transplanted. Seedlings of any available photoperiod-sensitive rice variety are used. The double-

transplanted crop gives yields higher than a single-transplanted crop.

We conducted a field trial on silty-clay loam soil at the Rajendra Agricultural University Farm, Pusa (Bihar) during wet season using six photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties—Janaki, BR8, T141, B14, C62-68, and Bakol (local check)—and three dates of transplanting—1 Sep, 16 Sep, and 1 Oct.

The trial was in a split-plot design, with date of transplanting in the main plot and varieties in subplots, with three replications. Kharuhan seedlings (30 d in first nursery + 45 d in the second) were

transplanted at 15- × 10-cm spacing with 2 seedlings/hill. A uniform 40 kg N, 8.8 kg P/ha was applied at transplanting. The crop was irrigated as needed and harvested in the second week of Dec.

The grain yield differed among varieties and with date of transplanting (see table). Variety C62-68 and Janaki gave significantly higher yields (C62-68 grain weight was lower than that of Janaki, but it had more grains/panicle).

Grain yield decreased significantly with delay in transplanting. The crop transplanted 16 Sep gave 27.6% lower grain yield than that transplanted 1 Sep; the 1 Oct crop gave 72.4% lower yield.

The variety by date of transplanting interaction also significantly influenced grain yield. Reduction in yield of C62-68 and Janaki due to delay in transplanting was less than that with other varieties.

Grain yield of double-transplanted, photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties by transplanting dates in flood-affected area of Pusa (Bihar), India.

	Grain yield (t/ha)			Mean
	1 Sep	16 Sep	1 Oct	
Janaki	3.6	2.7	1.2	2.5
BR8	2.2	2.2	0.9	1.8
T141	2.5	1.6	0.3	1.5
BR14	2.8	1.9	0.4	1.7
C62-68	3.8	3.0	1.5	2.8
Bakol (local check)	2.3	1.1	0.5	1.3
Mean	2.9	2.1	0.8	
LSD (0.05)				
For variety		0.3		
For date of transplanting		0.6		
For variety at same date of transplanting		0.5		
For date of transplanting of same variety		0.6		

Panicle exertion in the two varieties was complete even with the last transplanting date. This probably resulted in higher percentage of fertile spikelets in C62-68 and Janaki, and

consequently higher grain yields under extremely late transplanting. In other varieties, incomplete panicle exertion occurred with delay in transplanting. □

Effect of a new abscisic acid analog on chilled rice leaves

A. A. Flores and K. Dörffling, Institut für Allgemeine Botanik und Botanischer Garten, Universität Hamburg, Federal Republic of Germany; and B. S. Vergara, Plant Physiology Department, IRRRI

One factor that limits rice growth and yield in many rice-growing countries is chilling injury. One measure to minimize this problem is chemical treatment. New abscisic acid analogs developed by BASF, Ludwigshafen, FRG, and coded LAB 173711 and LAB 144143 have been reported to increase chilling tolerance in cucumber, tomato, and wheat.

We investigated the effects of the analog in chilled rice leaves.

Pregerminated seeds of IR42 and Fujisaka 5 were seeded directly in 1-liter pot containing Maahas soil and kept at 29/21 °C, 12 h photoperiod, and 80% relative humidity. Uniform seedlings were selected and sprayed with LAB 173711 at 10⁻³ mol/liter, and 10⁻⁴ mol/liter. After 24 h, plants were transferred to 5 °C for 1, 2, 3, 5, and d. After chilling exposure, they were returned to 29 °C for recovery.

1. Percent leaf area injury in LAB 173711-treated rice plants chilled at 5 °C for 24 h and transferred to 29 °C for recovery. Data are means ± SE of 10 measurements.

Damaged leaf area was observed visually (wilted and brown color) and estimated using the formula

$$\text{Injured leaf area (\%)} = \frac{\text{length of injured portion}}{\text{length of whole leaf blade}} \times 100$$

2. Differences in leaf fresh weight of LAB 173711-treated plants chilled at 5 °C and transferred to 29 °C for recovery. Data are means ± SE of 10 measurements.

Injured leaf area was markedly lower in LAB 173711-treated plants (Fig. 1), and leaf fresh weight in control was much lower than in LAB 173711-treated plants (Fig. 2). This protective effect of the applied abscisic acid analog may be due in part to its water conserving-activity. □